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Digital Technologies in Justice: Blockchain as an Innovative Way of Dispute Resolution

У статті досліджено потенціал технології блокчейн та розумних контрактів для вирішення спорів. Розглянуто децентралізовані платформи правосуддя, які використовують анонімних присяжних для ухвалення рішень на основі блокчейну. Ці платформи мають на меті забезпечити справедливе ставлення, унеможливаючи ухвалення рішень будь-якою одноосібною стороною, та сприяти передбачуваності. Децентралізована природа ухвалення рішень є ключовим аспектом, оскільки судові рішення ухвалюються не централізованим органом, схильним до упередженості, а спільнотою присяжних, які мотивовані діяти чесно. Розширюючи доступ до юридичних послуг, ці платформи потенційно можуть знизити витрати та затримки у судах. Ґрунтуючись на технології розумних контрактів, ці платформи дозволяють автоматично виконувати рішення з урегулювання спорів, що виникають при блокчейн-транзакціях, без участі державних судів чи централізованих інституцій, тим самим пропонуючи новаторський підхід до вирішення таких конфліктів

Висвітлено потенційні проблеми, пов'язані з цими платформами. Стереотипи, упередження та поведінкові фактори можуть впливати на процеси прийняття рішень присяжними. Технічні ризики, такі як можливість створення кількох облікових записів та відсутність особистої репутації, створюють можливості для змови та маніпулювання голосами. Крім того, виникають правові проблеми через несумісність платформ із законодавством деяких країн, оскільки їхній анонімний і конфіденційний характер суперечить принципам, таким як змагальне судочинство та прозорість, необхідним у системах цивільного права. Підкреслено необхідність подальших досліджень для вирішення правових, технологічних, поведінкових та економічних питань, пов'язаних із вирішенням спорів на основі блокчейну. Наголошено на важливості подолання регуляторних невизначеностей, дотримання конфіденційності й анонімності та узгодження впровадження цих платформ із чинними правовими рамками для забезпечення їх широкого прийняття та можливості виконання.

Ключові слова: цифровізація правосуддя, блокчейн, смарт-контракти, онлайн вирішення спорів, конфіденційність, нормативно-правове регулювання, платформи децентралізованого правосуддя, ухвалення рішень.

The article explores the potential of blockchain technology and smart contracts for dispute resolution. It examines decentralized justice platforms that leverage anonymous jurors motivated by economic incentives to make decisions based on blockchain. These platforms aim to ensure fair treatment by precluding any single entity from unilaterally making decisions and foster predictability by strictly adhering to encoded algorithms. The decentralized nature of decision-making is a crucial aspect, as judicial decisions are not made by a centralized body prone to bias but rather by a community of jurors incentivized to act honestly. By expanding access to legal services, these platforms can potentially lower costs and court delays. Grounded in smart contracts, they enable automatic enforcement of dispute resolution outcomes without involving state courts or centralized alternatives, offering a promising solution for resolving disputes arising from blockchain-based transactions.

However, the article highlights potential challenges associated with these platforms. Stereotypes, biases, and behavioral factors may influence jurors' decision-making processes. Technical risks, such as the ability to create multiple accounts and the lack of personal reputation, open the door for collusion and manipulation of votes. Additionally, legal challenges arise from the platforms' incompatibility with legislation in some countries, as their anonymous and confidential nature contradicts principles like adversarial proceedings and transparency required in civil law jurisdictions. The article underscores the need for further research to address legal, technological, behavioral, and economic issues related to blockchain-based dispute resolution. It emphasizes the importance of addressing regulatory uncertainties and aligning the implementation of these platforms with existing legal frameworks to ensure their widespread adoption and enforceability. Furthermore, the article advocates for studying privacy and anonymity concerns within the context of blockchain-based dispute resolution platforms.

Keywords: digitalization of justice, blockchain, smart contracts, online dispute resolution, confidentiality, legal regulation, decentralized justice platforms, decision-making.

Target setting. The modern judicial system is actively implementing digitalization by utilizing innovative technological solutions [1, 2]. The most promising technology is blockchain, which offers several advantages, including decentralization and immutability [3]. These characteristics enable conducting and tracking transactions without intermediaries. Blockchain can be used as a tool for automating contract execution. “Smart contracts” are computer programs that automatically execute contracts based on blockchain technology [4]. They are designed to ensure the execution and verification of contractual terms in a decentralized, transparent, secure, and reliable manner. Smart contracts record the terms of the contract in one of the programming languages and begin automatic execution of the contract according to pre-established conditions. When the conditions are met, the contract takes effect. Its main characteristics are decentralization and reliability. Such a contract is of high quality and difficult to forge. The use of blockchain-based smart contracts can effectively address traditional issues involving third parties, eliminate the influence of external factors, ensure the authenticity and reliability of

information, and prevent fraud. Smart contracts define the rights and obligations and protect the legitimate rights of both parties to the agreement [5].

Smart contracts offer several advantages, including their ability to execute automatically without human intervention. They provide public visibility of contract provisions on the blockchain, enable avoidance of financial crimes such as money laundering, and prevent contract abuses. However, this technology may introduce new risks while failing to address the issue of incomplete contracts and raising new questions. The need to specify all possible future scenarios in a smart contract is a complex and practically unfeasible task. This fact leads to increased costs of contract formulation, as parties must account for a vast array of potential action scenarios. Additionally, the automated execution of smart contracts eliminates flexibility in ensuring compliance, increasing the cost of anticipating sanctions for violations [6].

Due to the complexity and technical nature of smart contracts, it is almost impossible to fully avoid situations where discrepancies arise in interpreting their content or issues with their execution due to

inconsistencies and vulnerabilities. The question arises as to how such disagreements between parties should be resolved. For example, what will happen if the program is not executed by the contractual provisions due to unforeseen circumstances, or if an event not covered by the contract occurs? There is uncertainty regarding the mechanisms for resolving disputes related to smart contracts. In this regard, their implementation may create a new type of dispute that will require alternative blockchain-based conflict resolution mechanisms. Blockchain-based contracts are a source of new disputes that need to be resolved, but at the same time, they are a technology that provides an opportunity to develop new methods of dispute resolution [6]. Despite their potential, the implementation of blockchain in jurisprudence requires careful study and resolution of several legal, technological, and regulatory issues.

The purpose of the article is to analyze new blockchain-based dispute resolution mechanisms and explore the possibility of using electronic courts to regulate blockchain-based transactions.

Analyses of research and publications. The rapid development of blockchain technology and the spread of the Internet have led to the application of smart contract technology in various spheres. This fact has caused controversial discussions among scholars and practitioners. Particular attention is drawn to the regulatory uncertainty and legal implications of this innovative technology [5, 7–9]. Scholars Y. Aouidef and others have investigated the effectiveness of decentralized justice, a new approach to online dispute resolution that combines blockchain, crowdsourcing, and game theory [10]. A. Ferreira noted that in most legal systems, there are no serious obstacles to the implementation of smart contracts, but their regulation requires improving the legal framework [11]. Y. Gabuthy analyzed the blockchain-based dispute resolution platform Kleros, which is based on game theory. The author argued that in the future, competition is likely to arise between blockchain-based dispute resolution systems, the nature and outcome of which are difficult to predict. However, ethical and normative issues remain uncertain, which are critical for ensuring fairness [6]. A. Gudkov studied the key elements of procedural fairness that should be ensured by blockchain-based dispute resolution platforms [12]. Researchers A.M. Lane and C. Platz considered blockchain as an institutional technology that opens up new opportunities for regulating copyright. They studied the

implications of its impact on copyright law [13]. Authors S. Heidari and others analyzed the unique challenges that arise in enforcing smart contracts, including issues of evidence, the possibility of enforcing a waiver of defense, and uncertainty regarding jurisdiction and choice of law [14].

The statement of basic materials. Decentralized justice platforms are electronic courts that utilize blockchain technology and are designed to resolve disputes through jurors [15]. The dispute resolution process on these platforms is encrypted as smart contracts on the blockchain to eliminate any legal uncertainty. From this perspective, these mechanisms largely model online dispute resolution (ODR) processes, such as online negotiation or mediation, which emerged in the early 2000s to resolve disputes related to Internet transactions [16].

Decentralized justice platforms are built on blockchain technology. They function as a decentralized third party for the arbitration of disputes across a wide range of cases, such as e-commerce, insurance, and finance [17]. Specifically in Ukraine, a prototype blockchain-based real estate registry has been created. The proposed concept of cross-blockchains aims to automate the system based on smart contracts and decentralized applications. The developers of the prototype presented a protocol that forms the basis of “smart laws” – legal acts intended to regulate inheritance issues, dispute resolution, and other potential problems arising from law enforcement involving third parties within the use of blockchain technology. For now, this application is only a demo version and is intended to familiarize users with the process of real estate tokenization [18].

Such applications are designed to resolve disputes related to smart contracts. They can be activated immediately after a dispute arises during the execution of a smart contract. In this case, money transfers are frozen until the dispute is resolved. For this, the parties to the contract must choose a decentralized justice platform as the dispute resolution service provider in their smart contract in advance and agree on some basic features of the process [6]. For example, the court where the dispute will be heard, the size of the court, etc. If the parties agree, the digital platform randomly assigns self-selected jurors to resolve the dispute, who examine the evidence and vote on a decision. After that, the smart contract is executed by the decision representing the majority of votes. After this decision is made, tokens are redistributed among the jurors depending on whether their

vote aligns with the majority. A juror receives payment only if their vote is consistent with the others. The purpose of this process is to implement economic mechanisms that will make it more profitable for jurors to adhere to the truth than to conceal facts. Without the ability to communicate to coordinate their actions, the jurors will independently choose a focal decision that in a particular situation will be perceived by the majority as correct or logical [19]. The key assumption underlying this incentive mechanism is that those who disagreed with the majority verdict of the jurors either lacked sufficient experience to properly assess the case, did not consider all the evidence properly, or consciously did not seek to render a fair verdict. If one of the parties is dissatisfied with the jurors' decision, they can appeal it, and then the case will be reconsidered. However, the composition of the appeal panel is supplemented by one additional juror to the previous number. This approach aims to deter parties from numerous unfounded appeals, as with each new consideration, financial and time costs increase due to the involvement of additional jurors.

From a normative perspective, interesting elements of implementing a decision-making mechanism through decentralized justice platforms are the following:

1. Due to the immutability of the blockchain and the decentralized nature of the decision-making process, the system aims to uphold two key principles of justice: it seeks to ensure fair treatment, as no single person can make decisions alone; predictability of the outcome, since the parties to the conflict can be confident that the process will strictly follow the algorithm encoded. Based on a decentralized blockchain, such an application is aimed at guaranteeing the impartiality of decisions made through their collective adoption. However, the computational nature of the algorithm creates predictability of the process for the parties to the dispute.

2. The decentralized nature of the dispute resolution mechanism plays an important role, as the judicial decision is not made by a centralized body (e.g., a judge or arbitrator), which by definition can be biased. Instead, the decision is made by a community of jurors, who are not expected to be honest for moral reasons, but because the system environment motivates them to act honestly.

3. Traditional legal systems are relatively expensive, partly due to the monopoly on the provision of legal services. Lawyers have monopolized legal

advice, and judges have monopolized decision-making. The development of blockchain-based dispute resolution methods can help expand access to legal services and, consequently, lower market prices and court delays. Decentralized justice platforms cannot completely replace lawyers in civil cases, but they are capable of resolving certain types of disputes for which professional lawyers are not a viable option due to the high cost of their services.

Based on smart contracts, decentralized justice platforms ensure automatic enforcement of dispute resolution outcomes without the need to involve state courts or centralized alternatives.

However, the concept of such applications for the administration of justice has several potential issues. Such software is not immune to the influence of stereotypes and other biases as a way of reaching consensus. There are potential behavioral issues associated with the decision-making process by jurors in decentralized justice systems. For example, some jurors may face cognitive difficulties in properly processing case information and evidence. Others may identify themselves with one side of the conflict due to belonging to the same social/ethnic group and vote in its favor. There is also a risk that jurors will be guided by a desire to maintain a positive self-image rather than objectively evaluating the evidence (e.g., a juror may abstain from voting against a consumer in a dispute with a company in order not to feel guilty).

From a technical standpoint, the anonymous nature of users, the ability to create multiple accounts by one person, and the complete lack of personal reputation pave the way for various forms of manipulation on blockchain-based dispute resolution platforms. For example, some jurors may collude and coordinate their decisions by revealing their votes. One party may attempt to bribe jurors, promising a reward for a certain decision, or one juror may create multiple pseudo-accounts to exert undue influence on the outcome.

There are also legal issues, as the way blockchain dispute resolution platforms operate is incompatible with the legislation of some countries. For example, in France, according to the Code of Civil Procedure, the judge is required to ensure compliance with the principle of adversarial proceedings [20]. This implies that the defendant has sufficient time to prepare a defense, the identities of the parties are authenticated, and the parties can familiarize themselves with the case materials. However, these

conditions are not met on decentralized platforms, where anonymous parties submit evidence in their favor without discussion. The decision-maker effectively finds themselves in the role of an investigator, as the elements of the case can only be discussed after the verdict is rendered. However, on these platforms, decisions are not publicly announced. Therefore, the question of ensuring the legal force of decisions made by decentralized justice systems remains open, especially in civil law countries (e.g., Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Sweden, etc.) [6]. The claim of the possibility of creating effective self-enforcing dispute resolution mechanisms on top of national laws raises doubts. Anonymity, lack of adversarial proceedings, lack of transparency in the process, and confidentiality of decisions in decentralized judicial systems contradict the legal norms of many countries, casting doubt on the possibility of ensuring the enforcement of their verdicts.

Conclusions. The article analyzes innovative approaches to dispute resolution using blockchain technology. The potential of smart contracts for application in this area is examined. The mechanism of

decentralized blockchain-based justice platforms is investigated. The advantages and disadvantages of such platforms are considered, including ensuring impartiality, predictability, and automatic enforcement of decisions, risks of biases, manipulations, and issues regarding compliance with the principles of adversarial proceedings. The legal challenges of implementing decentralized blockchain-based dispute resolution mechanisms in various legal systems, especially in civil law countries, are analyzed. The need for further research to overcome legal, technological, and regulatory issues related to the use of blockchain in the justice system is outlined. Directions for further research include studying privacy and anonymity issues in the context of blockchain-based dispute resolution platforms.

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